

AMBEDKAR'S THOUGHTS ON LABOUR WELFARE

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Abstract:

Ambedkar had a lofty goal that the social ills that befell him in his youth should not befall the next generation. Ambedkar may have been the first Indian to receive a doctorate in economics. As an expert in economic education, he felt that the industrial development and agricultural development of the country should be considered as the two eyes of India. He consolidated agricultural lands fragmented into small and marginal lands and gave suggestions for higher yields in agriculture. He consolidated agricultural lands fragmented into small and marginal lands and gave suggestions for higher yields in agriculture. He consolidated agricultural lands fragmented into small and marginal lands and gave suggestions for higher yields in agriculture. He enacted legislation to establish a number of welfare schemes to encourage workers. He may be said to have caused a renaissance in land reform and revenue. 'I'm not like clay that dissolves easily in water. I, like the molten rock that diverts rivers. I will never lose my uniqueness wherever I am and no matter what kind of friendship I find.' Such militancy may have prompted him to formulate welfare schemes for the advancement of labor.

Keywords: *Ambedkar and Labour welfare, Ambedkar and Women Empowerment, Ambedkar and Indian economy.*

Introduction:

Ambedkar found unequal social inequality as an obstacle to the growth of the Indian economy. He thought of the fragmented farms and the interests and rights of the workers who were exploited on the basis of caste. He also mentioned in his books about public and private companies. His norm for economic development was globalization, liberalization and privatization. He may have contributed to the development of various sectors such as railways, spinning mills and mining.

Ambedkar's Thoughts on Labour welfare:

Ambedkar may have been instrumental in speeding up the process for the rights and interests of all workers, regardless of gender. In particular, Ambedkar called for the creation of new jobs through the "Mahatma Gandhi National Employment Guarantee Scheme" and for the expansion of the scheme for more creative work."

Ambedkar vehemently opposed the revenue and its structure. He spoke out against the burdensome taxation."Taxation should be less for the poor and more for the rich. There should be equality between different categories in taxation. Tax should not lead to reduction of living standards of the people. Land income tax should be very flexible and should not tax agricultural lands.

The position taken by the Ambedkar Finance Commission to reduce the tax burden on the people is also noteworthy. "In 1951, Ambedkar established the Finance Commission of India. He made it a policy that low-income people do not need income tax." Ambedkar acted in the best interests of the workers. He realized that the country's water resources should be improved for agriculture to flourish. Therefore, he took the initiative for river integration as the best advice for water resources management. When he was the Minister of Labor, Irrigation and Power, he recommended an integrated approach to the optimal use of water resources. To that end, he said, an autonomous power should be established that would give the central government a greater share.

He provided the framework for the legal approach to this approach when drafting the constitution. Later, he carried out this work in accordance with the policy framework that led to the establishment of the Damodar Valley Project (in Bihar and West Bengal). He suggested for the first time that the Krishna, Godavari and Thapti rivers should be connected to each other." Realizing that agriculture is the key to the development of the country, he took appropriate action for water management. Ambedkar deeply regretted the plight of the slave population in the face of religious and economic exploitation. "The caste system is not just a division of labor, it is a division of workers," he said. Ifu is not based on natural attitudes or abilities. This is the biggest obstacle to economic growth.

This method can lead to inefficient production. It also reduces the movement of workers. Untouchability is worse than slavery. This is the system of exploitation." he Commented. Ambedkar wanted to create a world of new workers through his education. He considered the country's limited legal framework to prevent all the forces of young labor from being used for productivity.

He thought of industrialization and agricultural development. "He pioneered the promotion of agriculture as India's primary industry." Ambedkar emphasized education, public health, social welfare, housing facilities, etc. for the benefit of industry and workers. He said industries should be nationalized to ensure social and economic justice in the country. He said the commonwealth economy was the best for the development of the country. He was heartened to see the untouchability that existed among the workers in the Bombay mills. He noted that caste divides not only the profession but also the workers. He also clarified that caste was a major obstacle in mobilizing workers as a class. He started the Independent Workers' Party in 1936 with the aim of mobilizing working people across castes.

In 1938 he presided over a conference of the oppressed class working in the railways in Manmad. "For me, the workers of this country have to fight two enemies. One - the Brahmanism of the upper caste and two - the bourgeoisie 'and declares that Brahmanism is the opposite of freedom, equality and fraternity. He advised the workers that our goal was to get rid of this notion of wage slavery and achieve the principle of liberation.

Welfare Schemes for Female Workers

Ambedkar said, "The progress of a society can only be measured through the measure of women's advancement." He stressed that the protection of the law should be common to all, regardless of gender. He advised that every member should be given unequal value.

- Gender equality
- Girls' education
- Hindu Code Bill - On the divisions framed by Hinduism.
- Maternity Bill - On pre and post maternity leave.

He gave women an equal voice in professional contributions like men. Ambedkar's work included the introduction of a workers' insurance scheme, the introduction of in-house pricing, and a ban on the employment of female workers in deep mines. One who believes that government spending should include faith, knowledge, and the economy.

Conclusion:

Ambedkar's policies cannot be categorized as caste based. His economic response is as to the human general. An economic architect, Ambedkar redesigned the old unreformed economic policies of his time and integrated both industry and agriculture as elements of national development. He has formulated policies for the development of the industry by uniting all, irrespective of gender. It is noteworthy that, India's first river confluence - the Damodar Valley Project, a proud river valley project was created by Ambedkar.

References

1. S. N. Mishra (2010). *Socio-economic and Political Vision of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar*. New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company. pp. 173–174.
2. <https://www.sociologygroup.com/research-on-ambedkar-and-his-economic/>
3. Ingle, M R (September 2010). "Relevance of Dr. Ambedkar's Economic Philosophy in the Current Scenario"(PDF). *International Research Journal*. I (12). Archived from the original (PDF) on 20 October 2013. Retrieved 19 October 2013.
4. Ambirajan, S. (1999). "Ambedkar's Contributions to Indian Economics". *Economic and Political Weekly*. 34 (46/47): 3280–3285.
5. *Socio-economic and political vision of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar / edited by S.N. Mishra* New Delhi: Concept Pub. Co., 2010
6. Mishra, S.N., ed. (2010). *Socio-economic and political vision of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar*. New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company. pp. 173–174.
7. *Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar: Writing and speeches "I Measure the progress of the community by the degree of progress which women have attained" Vol – I P – 466*
8. *Dr.Ambedkar". National Campaign on Dalit Human Rights*. Archived from the original on 8 October 2012. Retrieved 12 January 2012.